

Risk-based analysis and policy implications for renewable energy investments in Greece

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Abstract

Significant renewable energy (RE) investments have to be realized in order to achieve the ambitious RE targets set in the EU for 2020 and beyond. Moreover, a great amount of capital has to be leveraged, as these projects are followed by high investment and financing costs. Main aim of this paper is the provision of a comprehensive assessment of the existing risk elements of RE investments in relation to the respective policies and the evaluation of their impact on the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) in Greece. A significant consultation with key national energy stakeholders took also place, including policy makers, project developers, investors, equity providers, bankers and energy analysts in the Greek RE market, in order to provide a validation of the respective results. It has been concluded that the policy design risk represents the risk element with the greatest impact on the cost of capital and, thus, the level of RE investments' deployment. Moreover, based on the cost of capital valuation process followed, the WACC was estimated to reach approximately 12% for onshore wind and little lower values for solar PV projects in Greece.

Keywords: policy risk; onshore wind; solar PV; weighted average cost of capital; energy policy; Greece.

Highlights:

- Policy design risk constitutes the main influential parameter of the WACC.
- Social acceptance is more critical for large-scale, mainly onshore wind, projects.
- A stable policy framework may lead to less risk and, thus, cost of RE projects.
- The WACC is around 12% for onshore wind and little lower for solar PV projects.

1. Introduction

In the context of the Energy Union established (EC, 2015), the European Union (EU) is committed to become the leader in renewable energy (RE) development at a global level. The extended implementation of RE investments constitutes a necessity in order to achieve the national binding targets set by Directive 2009/28/EC in EU Member States for 2020 (EC, 2009).

On the ground of the EU Directive 2009/28/EC, Law 3851/2010 determines ambitious national targets for renewable energy sources (RES) in Greece by 2020 (Governmental Gazette 85/4-6-2010). In addition, the European Commission has also set ambitious EU climate and energy goals for 2030, including an increase of the share of renewable energy in final energy consumption by at least 27% at EU level (EC, 2016; European Council, 2014).

In order these sustainable energy objectives to be fulfilled, extensive investments have to be implemented in the RE sector during the upcoming years (IRENA, 2016a). These capital intensive investments are followed by high upfront costs and, in most cases, low operation and maintenance costs (IRENA, 2016b; Liu et al., 2016; Lee and Zhong, 2015; Abdmouleh et al., 2015; Dai et al., 2016). Due to the economic nature of these projects, the financing costs are critical and constitute a considerable part of the overall cost of renewables (IEA, 2015).

Main influential parameters of the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) produced by RE projects are, among others, the initial investment expenditures (upfront payments) and the discount rate, which reflects the costs of capital of the investment, i.e. the rate at which net cash flow future values are being discounted against current values (Ouyang and Lin, 2014; IRENA, 2012).

The weighted average cost of capital (WACC) has been identified as a key financial indicator that efficiently represents the cost of capital in a considerable amount of literature (Donovan and Corbishley, 2016; Byrnes et al., 2016; IRENA, 2015; de Jager et al., 2011; Gross et al., 2010). In particular, the WACC has emerged as an effective and efficient tool in capturing the real cost of capital of investments and an understandable and easily applicable indicator in projects' profitability assessments that provides the minimum acceptable rate of return at which

an investor is willing to invest capital in a particular project (Mir-Artigues and del Rio, 2014). The economic profitability of an investment may be accessed through the comparison of the internal rate of return (IRR) of this project with the respective WACC (EIB, 2013).

Specifically, this financial indicator is defined as the weighted sum of both the cost of equity and debt capital, based on their particular shares on the total funding capital, and represents the opportunity cost of these capital components, i.e. equity and debt, that are invested in a particular project (UNDP, 2014).

Moreover, the importance of the cost of capital on the total cost of RE investments is expected to be enhanced in the future due to the declining installation (mainly equipment) costs of both wind and solar power projects (IRENA, 2016c). This is mainly based on the fact that the financial costs are expected to become an even greater part of the total levelized cost of electricity produced by renewables as all the other cost components are facing a constant decline over time. This impact is also augmented by the fact that the cost of capital is highly affected by existing investment risks (IRENA, 2016a; Arnold and Yildiz, 2015; Gross et al., 2010; Mitchell et al., 2006).

In this respect, the sustainable energy transition depends on the opportunity of RE markets to attract high amounts of capital (IRENA, 2016a; Masini and Menichetti, 2012). This may be applied via a stable and efficient policy and regulatory framework and a well-functioning RE market (IEA-RETD, 2016), as the established policy targets and the respective policy actions exert a critical role in the deployment of RE investments (Masini and Menichetti, 2012). Specifically, the smooth integration of renewables in an efficiently designed and well-functioning energy (electricity) market is deemed necessary in the mid-term. In this context, the cost of capital is identified as a key driver for enhancing competitiveness of RE investments and, thus, facilitate the extended implementation of these projects (IRENA, 2016b; DIA-CORE, 2016).

The feed-in tariff (FIT) scheme has been the most commonly applied mechanism for supporting RE projects in most European countries (Jenner et al., 2013; Lüthi and Wüstenhagen, 2012). The high levels of effectiveness and cost efficiency, as well as the low risk premiums and secure returns to RE investors are the main advantages of the FIT system (Abdmouleh et al., 2015; Ecofys, 2014; NREL, 2010). Even though the FIT has been proved to best mitigate risks for investors, the inadequate formulation of the tariffs, not in line with the real and gradual declining RE investment costs, may lead to distortions in the energy market (Ecofys, 2014). In addition, the maintenance of guaranteed remuneration level for RE projects may result in adverse effects on competitiveness and, thus, to less investments, due to the absence of credibility at the long-term level, and, therefore, future policy actions for further mitigation of RE applications' cost (Kwon, 2015; Criscuolo and Menon, 2015).

The fixed and regulated tariffs and the clear tariff degression introduced in Germany have been the main determinants for the increased investors' confidence and the extensive development of RE projects in the country (Liou, 2015). In addition, the long contract period (of 20 years) along with the guaranteed grid priority have been additional critical parameters that facilitated the extended financing of RE projects at low interest rates and the creation of a stable investment environment (Pegels and Lütkenhorst, 2014; Mabee et al., 2012).

Changes of the legislative framework, including, among others, alterations of the FITs and retroactive actions, may lead to an uncertain economic environment, negative effects on RES project's profitability and a less favorable investment environment for investors (Frantál and Prousek, 2016). Several retroactive changes of policies have been already taken in several countries of the EU, including Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Greece, Italy and Spain, leading to negative effects on the RE investment environment of these countries (de la Hoz et al., 2016; SolarPower Europe, 2015; Di Dio et al., 2015). Retroactive policy actions have taken place in Belgium, in 2013, as the implemented reforms of the Flemish RE support mechanism led into changes of the tradable green certificates (TGC) including a limitation of the TGC eligibility to 10 years for units already commissioned (El Kasmioui et al., 2015). In December

2013, a 20% tax has been imposed by the Bulgarian government on the income of wind and solar PV energy producers (Keep on Track, 2015). Retroactive legislation has been also introduced in Czech Republic, in 2010, with a tax of 26% for PV projects of installed capacity greater than 30kW (Janda and Tyulebekov, 2016). In Italy, the Legislative Decree No. 91, issued by the Italian Government, has also resulted into retroactive impacts on incentives for PV projects (Di Dio et al., 2015). For the case of Spain, the Royal Decree-Law 9/2013 has introduced retroactive reduction of the FIT levels for all RE producers (Gallego-Castillo and Victoria, 2015).

Regarding the policy costs induced by renewables, their control is vulnerable under a FIT policy scheme as the prediction of the market uptake's rate is deemed difficult with no intermediate caps or capacity-based degression (Helapco, 2010). In several EU countries, such as Italy and Spain, the enormous growth of the solar PV market, as a result of the excess FITs provided, has led into considerable policy costs and enlarged electricity deficits (Ecofys, 2014). On the contrary, regular tariff formulation, on the ground of adjustment formulae related to market growth, is identified as an effective way of efficiently managing policy costs and, in parallel, avoiding negative effects to the RE investment environment (Ragwitz and Rathmann, 2011). Therefore, a fixed premium scheme is considered more favorable to less uncertain policy costs (Ecofys, 2014).

According to the European Commission's Guidelines on State aid for environmental protection and energy 2014-2020, the FIT scheme will remain active solely for small-scale RE projects and the transition to feed-in premium (FIP) or tendering and auctioning mechanisms will be mandatory, leading to competitive bidding processes for RE remuneration (EC, 2014a). The maturity of RE technologies along with the need for increased cost-effectiveness and reduction of current distortions have been the most decisive reasons for the gradual introduction of competitive bidding processes in the support of RE projects by the EU (EC, 2014b; EC, 2013). This transition is also promoted in the context of the Energy Union, which aims to effectively deal with market failures, guarantee effectiveness in terms of costs and avoid phenomena of

excess compensation (EC, 2015). In this context, market-oriented policy measures and mechanisms are critical to be implemented in order to facilitate the augmentation of RE competitiveness (Eurelectric, 2014), aiming at both the reduction of the generation cost of RE applications and the attraction of external financiers' participation for providing their capital in sufficiently profitable investment options (Lee and Zhong, 2015).

Main aim of this paper is to assess the risks elements related to RE investments and quantify the cost of capital for onshore wind and solar PV projects in Greece. This study of analyzing risks and quantifying the cost of capital for RE investments in Greece is driven by the following questions:

- Which risks are influencing investments in the RE sector?
- How policies have affected these risks?
- Which is the expected return for a RE investor in Greece?

Within this framework, the WACC has been selected as the most appropriate financial indicator that reflects the risk environment in the country. The quantification of the WACC has been implemented via the application of the related financial models suggested by the scientific literature and the extracted results have been validated through numerous interviews with policy makers, project developers, investors, equity providers, bankers and energy analysts in the national RE market. In addition, a series of workshops has been implemented in order to reach a broader audience and receive feedback on the research results. Therefore, the involvement of the national energy experts in the assessment of the most critical risk elements of RE projects in Greece and the quantification of the respective cost of capital increases the validity of the study's extracted outcomes.

The development of the most mature and widely applied RE technologies, namely onshore wind and solar PV, and the respective policies adopted in Greece are presented in Section 2. Section 3 introduces the theoretical model applied and describes the consultation procedure followed for the validation of this methodological approach and its extracted outcomes. The

model and interviews' results are incorporated into Section 4 along with a related discussion. Finally, the concluding remarks and fields for future research are provided in Section 5.

2. Renewable energy development in Greece

2.1 Energy mix in Greece

The energy mix in Greece, i.e. the share of each energy source in the gross inland consumption, is graphically depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. National share of fuels in gross inland energy consumption, 2015 – total consumption for 2015: 24.4 Mtoe

Based on the current national energy mix, the petroleum products represent almost the half of the total gross inland consumption and the renewables cover the 10% proportion of it.

Regarding the gross final energy consumption, in which the transformation output (electricity or heat produced from other sources of energy) is included, the 15.3% share of it is provided by RES for the year 2014 (Eurostat, 2016), with the national target being 20% by 2020 (Governmental Gazette 85/4-6-2010).

In addition, the national electricity mix, displaying the proportions of several energy sources in the gross final electricity consumption, is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Shares of energy sources in the gross final electricity consumption in Greece, 2016

Based on this electricity mix, renewable energy represents the 17.4% of the total electricity consumption in Greece for the year 2016.

2.2 Wind power progress in Greece

During the period from 2005 to 2015, the onshore wind installed capacity has been quadrupled and more than 1.5GW of new power capacity has been installed in Greece (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Cumulative installed onshore wind power capacity (in MW) in Greece

Regarding the net additions of onshore wind power capacity, Figure 4 presents a graphical illustration of the new annual capacities installed during the examined period.

Figure 4. Net additions of annual installed onshore wind power capacity (in MW) in Greece

The new additions of installed onshore wind power capacity followed a constant increase during the period 2006-2015, except from a couple of years of higher (2006 and 2011) and lower (2007 and 2013) growth. The current status of onshore wind installed capacity is still far from the national target (7,200MW) set by 2020 (Greek Ministry of Energy & Environment, 2010). However, due to the significant reduction of the country's gross final energy consumption in the recent years, it is estimated that even a lower, but in any case continuous, increase of wind generation will provide adequate contribution towards the final achievement of Greece's 2020 target.

2.3 Solar PV power progress in Greece

During the period from 2005 to 2015, the solar PV installed capacity has shown a considerable development and, approximately, 2,600MW of new solar PV power plants have been installed in Greece (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Cumulative installed solar PV power capacity (in MW) in Greece

Figure 6 presents a graphical illustration of the net annual additions of solar PV installed capacity.

Figure 6. Net additions of annual installed solar PV power installed capacity (in MW) in Greece

It is clearly visible that the boom in the development of solar PV projects in Greece, during the period 2011-2013, has been implemented as a result of the great economic attractiveness of these investments, leading to the fulfillment of 2020 national solar PV energy targets (2,200MW) already from 2013. However, this short-lived boom has led to long-term significant burden of electricity bills with high RE levy component. Greek policy makers, worried by this

development, reacted by actually freezing new solar PV projects even if these would have required just a fraction of the past compensation levels.

2.4 Policy Support Scheme

The FIT mechanism was the only support scheme in operation, along with capital grants in the framework of both national “incentives investment law” or EU’s structural and investment funds, for RE investments in Greece. After the period of high growth of renewables (period 2011-2013), during which high remuneration levels for RE projects were provided (see Law 3851/2010), the guaranteed payments for RE installments, mainly solar PV, incurred a considerable decrease through the adoption of the “New Deal” Law 4254/2014. Countries with similar weather characteristics to Greece, like Spain and Portugal, have also implemented the FIT mechanism in order to facilitate, mainly, solar PV technology expansion in their territories. In addition, Italy and France have applied quota systems and tax reduction mechanisms, except from the FIT scheme, in order to promote renewable energy development (EC, 2013).

In 2016, a new scheme has been established by the Greek Law 4414/2016 for the support of RE projects that start operation from the 1st January 2017, including a sliding FIP mechanism and tendering procedures. Main objectives of this scheme are the gradual integration of renewables into the electricity market and the reduction of funding support to RE projects, being also in line, as already mentioned, with the EU Guidelines on State aid for environmental protection and energy 2014-2020 (EC, 2014a). This transition from guaranteed RE support schemes to market-based instruments is included in the overall EU strategy for gradual phase-out of traditional, strictly regulated, remuneration systems (EC, 2015).

Specifically, the main structure of the sliding FIP scheme incorporates the direct participation of RE plants into the Greek wholesale electricity market. The RE producer sells the forecasted energy into the day-ahead market and receives the wholesale market price. Currently, this is the hourly system marginal price (SMP) of the day-ahead market. If the SMP is lower than a technology-specific “reference price” then the Operator of the Electricity Market (LAGIE) pays

the difference (sliding premium) between the SMP and the reference price (sliding FIP) to the RE producers. Participating in the day-ahead market may result in imbalance costs for the RE producer in case there is deviation, exceeding a certain tolerance threshold, between the forecasted and the actually produced and purchased energy. Moreover, the RE producers will not be paid the premium for a share of energy during periods with constant zero values of the SMP in the day-ahead market.

In 2016, the reference prices for new RE projects are administratively set at 98 €/MWh for wind projects and from the 1st of January 2017 and beyond, the reference prices for new RE projects are set through competitive tendering procedures. Pilot tendering procedures have been successfully completed in December 2016 for 40MW of solar PV power plants. In particular, the lowest bid for the 1st category of solar PV projects (<1MW) was 94.97€/MWh and for the 2nd category of solar PV projects (>1MW) the lowest bid was 79.97€/MWh (RAE, 2016).

Table 1. Remuneration levels for wind and solar PV power projects in Greece (€/MWh) – Based on Law 4414/2016

The FIT, which has been the prevailing RE policy support mechanism in Greece up to 2016, addresses risks through priority, grid access and, in general, entails risk of retroactive changes of RE policies. The FIT support scheme will continue to be operated for all new RE projects with maximum installed capacity of 3MW for onshore wind parks and 0.5MW for solar PVs. In addition, the already operated RE projects and those that have signed sales contract with LAGIE till 31.12.2015 will remain at the current FIT support scheme.

It should be noted that the data analysis does not include the FIP and the tender policy support schemes in 2016/2017.

3. Methodology and Data

The several risk elements for onshore wind and solar PV investments have been assessed and the cost of capital of the respective RE projects has been quantified, for the case of Greece, via

the application of a related theoretical model. This research analysis has been validated via the conduction of targeted interviews and workshops, in which numerous key national energy stakeholders participated.

The methodology for the assessment of risk elements and the quantification of the WACC for RE projects is grounded on the paper of Angelopoulos et al. (2016). Through an extensive literature review, the most important risk elements related to these investments have been identified (Byrnes et al., 2016; Dóci and Gotchev, 2016; Gatzert and Kosub, 2016; Jin et al., 2014; Wing and Jin, 2015; Stigka et al., 2014). Specifically, the relevant risks, associated with the three RE development stages (planning, construction and operation), have been assessed and further analyzed with the RE experts (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Renewable energy risk elements

It is considered that the presented risk elements, except from the country risk which is deemed a horizontal risk for all investments in a specific country, are covering the total spectrum of risk components that have influence on RE investments.

Other measures capturing risks are also the contract period and the debt maturity. In particular, shorter contract periods may lead into greater total electricity prices and, thus, a higher financing risk and raised price premiums (Wiser and Pickle, 1997). In general, governments may oblige debt providers to offer long-term contracts leading to reduced risk premium and, thus, cost of financing (de Jager and Rathmann, 2008). Except from the debt interest rate (cost of debt), the debt maturity (or debt term), i.e. the specific length of a loan, constitutes another factor that exerts a critical impact on the levelized costs of electricity produced from renewables. In general, increased investment risks result into lower debt maturity leading, thus, to a total increase of the cost of electricity produced from renewables (Wiser and Pickle, 1997).

In particular, the mathematical formulas applied for the calculation of the WACC and their related components are included in Table 2.

Table 2. Calculation formulas of the financial indicators

The quantification of the cost of equity has been implemented via the application of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM). For the case of the baseline rate, the one-year average of the 10-year Greek government bond yield has been used. The calculation of the beta coefficient has been grounded on the statistical analysis of TERNA Energy's returns, of an enterprise with a wide and diversified RE portfolio in the Greek energy market. The exact methodological approach followed for the quantification of the beta coefficient is the one provided by Angelopoulos et al. (2016). Moreover, the market risk premium (MRP) data used have been derived from the study of Fernandez et al. (2013).

Two different approaches have been utilized for the calculation of the cost of debt, which are proposed by Eurelectric (2012) and BNEF (2013). In particular, the one-year average 10-year German government bond yield has been used as a representative European risk-free rate in the former modeling approach. In addition, the credit default spread (CDS) of Greece and the renewable energy project spreads have been also taken into consideration, assumed equal to 3% and 3.5% for onshore wind and solar PV projects, respectively (Levin M., 2012). The Term Swap Interest rate is used as an indicative EU-level risk-free rate. In this approach, the country risk is represented by the surplus between the Greek and the German one-year average 10-year government bond yield. A typical financing structure of 70% debt and 30% equity capital has been assumed for both onshore wind and solar PV investments (Klessmann et al., 2013).

The respective input parameters for the quantification of the WACC, based on the theoretical modeling approach applied, are included in Table 3.

Table 3. Input data for the cost of capital calculation model

The main weakness of the applied modelling approach was the absence of return data for solely onshore wind and PV projects, as the key players in the Greek RE market have a broader portfolio that, most of the times, includes different RE technology options. As a result, a

uniform beta coefficient has been calculated for both onshore wind and solar PV projects and, thus, a unique cost of equity has been extracted for these two RE applications in Greece.

Representatives and experts from the national RE sector, including policy makers, project developers, investors, equity providers, bankers and energy consultants, have been approached and participated into the interviews procedure that took place during the period from October 2014 till April 2015. In particular, structured interviews were conducted with 43 national energy experts, including 2 experts from the respective Ministry, 5 experts from energy providers and the Public Power Corporation (PPC), 15 energy consultants, 10 RE project developers, 3 members of the academic community and 8 investors (among which members from banks and funding organizations). The sample of interviewees has been appropriately selected in order to achieve the greatest possible representativeness of the key actors in the Greek RE market. The interview procedure consisted of 5 different stages.

During the 1st stage, the theoretical model followed for the quantification of the respective financial indicators for RE projects was presented. In particular, the nine different risk categories identified and the possible decomposition of the cost of equity among them were provided. In this context, interviewees were questioned whether there are any risk elements missing and which elements have the highest and lowest impact on the cost of equity. In addition, all interviewees expressed their views on the risk elements related to RE investments by providing either quantitative (values or ranges of the risk premiums) or/and qualitative (ranking of the respective risk elements) feedback, with the proportion of complete numerical answers received to reach approximately 88% (38 out of 43 interviewees estimated the individual risk premiums).

The 2nd part of the interviews included a special focus on the policy-related risks. More specifically, the energy experts were questioned whether the renewable energy policy measures taken, during the first half of current decade, have resulted into alterations of the respective risk elements. Additionally, the surveys' participants were asked to rank, in terms of effectiveness,

the existing RE policies in the direction of mitigating the related risks. Specifically, the effectiveness of the adopted renewable energy policies in reducing the relevant risk categories has been ranked equal to “2”, on a scale from 1-5, where “1” represented the absence of influence and “5” the highest influence on reducing the underlying risks.

During the 3rd phase, the model results have been presented to the energy experts in order to share their views on the value of each one of the examined financial indicators. For the case of onshore wind power projects, the feedback of the energy experts on the assessment and quantification of the cost of capital was higher (36 complete responses) compared to solar PV projects (33 complete responses). The questionnaire of the respective interviews is presented in Appendix A.

Moreover, in November 2015, a one-day Workshop took place with the active participation of more than 75 participants, including the interviewees and the general public. Main topics of this policy event were the analysis of the existing risks, support mechanisms and cost of capital of RE investments and the implementation of a fruitful discussion on the research results extracted based on the proposed theoretical model conducted and the interviews implemented. Regarding the latter, most participants expressed their views that the research outcomes adequately depicted the RE investment environment in Greece and that appropriate policy decisions have to be implemented in order to mitigate the respective risk elements.

During the fourth phase, from June 2016 to October 2016, an additional series of interviews has been implemented with 9 selected stakeholders in order to update the previous analysis, with a clear focus on the solar PV market. During this phase, a 2nd Workshop has been also implemented in November 2016 in which more than 40 experts from the respective Ministry, the national regulator, RES industry associations, energy agencies and members of the scientific community cooperated. The new regulatory and policy framework formed and the potential consequences of the new developments were included in this analysis.

At the final stage, a third round of interviews has been conducted, from September 2016 to December 2016, identical to that of the first interviews' phase, in order to provide an update of the respective financial data for both RE technologies, for the year 2016. The questionnaire template and the interviews' steps followed have been almost the same and the project outcomes facilitated the extraction of fruitful and constructive conclusions regarding the evolution of the cost of capital of RE applications overtime in Greece.

The final outcomes of these interviews and workshops are given in the following sub-sections.

4. Results and Policy Implications

4.1 Risk Elements

At the first stage of the interviews, the participated experts provided an assessment of the severity of each risk element for RE investments in Greece and a ranking of them based on their significance in the RE investment decision making. In particular, the interviewees expressed their views on the risk elements related to RE investments and concluded that the three most important risk components were the policy design, financing and social acceptance risks.

The policy design risk has been identified as the most critical risk component towards RE development, as it is also pinpointed in the scientific literature (Gatzert and Vogl, 2016; Gatzert and Kosub, 2016; Lüthi and Wüstenhagen, 2012). The design of the policy support mechanism may result into critical implications to the risk profile of a RE project, which are currently included in the policy design risk element (DIA-CORE, 2016). This risk component is highly related to the policy actions that take place, a more detailed discussion on which is given in Section 4.2.

Regarding the RE financing risk, the need for finding alternative sources of capital, including “green” financial institutions or banks, and the creation of related funds, have been expressed as issues of major importance in order to boost further RE development in Greece.

Most of the energy experts also highlighted that the social acceptance risk constitutes an important risk element and receives greater values for the case of onshore wind than solar PV energy investments. One reason for this difference is the citizens' resistance against the development of large-scale onshore wind farms, mainly, due to the visual disturbance of landscape perception and the hypothetical impact on the fauna of the region close to these plants. Consequently, the regional character of this risk element is critical to be noted. Some interviewees responded also that the level of this risk shows deviations among the different regions in Greece, as citizens are more skeptics towards the penetration of onshore wind power plants in regions with increased tourism and, generally, in rural areas.

For large-scale onshore wind farms, grid access risk might be higher than for small-scale projects. High penetration of RE into the existing national power network requires additional infrastructures and extension actions, including new Medium Voltage substations and, possible, significant submarine interconnections, as existing grids are saturated or near saturation. The interconnection of the Cyclades islands and Crete to the mainland power system is characterized from most interviewees as projects of high significance for further exploitation of renewables' potential in the country. An additional related risk element that occurs is the way by which these grid investments, which are followed by considerable initial investment expenditures, will be financed, by either the RE producers or the final consumers.

Except from the technical and management risk which has been characterized as the least important risk component, the other risk elements, i.e. administrative, sudden policy change and market design and regulatory risks, generally have a reduced impact on RE investments, followed by non-zero risk premium margins, and have to be also taken into consideration for investment decision making, as also highlighted in the study of Doukas et al. (2011).

Specifically, the market design and regulatory risk was stated as the risk component that will be mainly affected by the gradual phase-out of guaranteed remuneration mechanisms (FIT) and the transition to market-based support schemes (sliding FIP) introduced in the national RE

market. A stable investment framework is considered crucial to facilitate the implementation of RE investments as this results into reduced cost of financing (EC, 2015). The retroactive reduction of the FIT levels and the impose of additional tax on RE producers are indicative examples of measures that took place during the previous period in the Greek RE market and are directly related to the sudden policy change risk. Thus, the uncertainty incurred by any sudden and retro-active change is represented by the sudden policy change risk. In terms of administrative procedures, extra uncertainty arises from considerable delays in issuing the necessary permits and, thus, the final implementation of RE projects. For a detailed description of the overall RE risk elements examined in current paper see DIA-CORE (2016).

An additional RE investment risk element noted by the energy experts was the non-established, when the interviews were conducted, RE targets till 2030 and beyond at EU level and the evolution of the SMP in the Greek power market. The former risk element has been eliminated as the European Union has shown a considerable and constant decisiveness on the enhanced promotion of RE investments, through the establishment of targets beyond 2020 (European Council, 2014). The latter risk element is directly related to the future design of the electricity markets and the integration of RE projects into them, being an element that has been already identified by the national energy policy bodies.

The following spider diagram (Figure 8) reveals the final intensity of the risk elements (highest: 8, lowest: 1) related to RE projects, as determined by the interviewees.

Figure 8. Importance of renewable energy risk elements as ranked by interviewees

Moreover, survey participants provided values or ranges for the set of risk premiums related to each risk element identified and the respective results are also presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Premiums for the risk elements based on interviews

The country risk constitutes, by far, the risk parameter with the greatest impact on RE investments in Greece, as highlighted by all interviewees. The country risk, represented by the

10-year national government bond yield, may not be addressed and, thus, reduced via energy policy measures, as it is grounded on the general economic environment and the financial circumstances in the country. Therefore, it adds further barriers on the extended implementation of RE investments in Greece.

4.2 Renewable Energy Policies in Greece

The interview participants analyzed the past and current situation of the RE policy actions and measures applied in Greece, focusing on the specific risk component of policy design risk, during the second phase of the interviews procedure.

At first, the energy experts specified the exact policy measures and changes that took place during the period from 2010 to 2015 and their impact on the policy-related risks. Within this framework, the intense taxes on RE producers, the delay in the decline of guaranteed remuneration of RE projects, similar to the respective technology learning curve, and the adverse financial circumstances in Greece constitute the main elements that negatively affected the investment risk environment of this sector.

In particular, the adoption of the Law 4254/2014 has been the most critical policy action that directly affected the development of RE technologies in the national energy system, imposing both negative and positive effects on the energy market. The retroactive and significant reduction of the FITs for solar PV power plants' compensation has initially resulted into a rise of the respective investment risk, mainly, for already operational projects in Greece.

The retroactive changes imposed to RE producers by the "New Deal" law were dual. Firstly, a drastic reduction of the FIT levels for operating RE projects was introduced, with the solar PV projects to manage the greatest reductions. Secondly, the RE producers of all technologies, except from the roof-top solar PV installations, were asked to financially contribute with a minimum of 10%, and up to 37.5% for solar PV projects, of their income in 2013 to the national electricity market operator (LAGIE) with the aim to eliminate its fund deficit until the end of 2014 (Governmental Gazette 85/07-04-2014).

On the other hand, some energy experts argued that the revised FIT scheme has mitigated the overall investment risk, along with the respective return on equity, for the case of new power plants and contributed to the improvement of the investment environment as it led to the considerable reduction of the electricity deficit in the Greek RE sector.

It is considered that any decline in the remuneration level of an investment increases, in general, the probability of credit default (debt recovery), and hence, increases risk exposure if investment expenditures remain unchanged. Nevertheless, because of the constantly declining costs of RE technologies that are translated into mitigated investment expenditures, the reduced remuneration levels may not lead into worsened risk exposure, but solely keep it constant. This situation is mainly applicable when the tariff depression rate utilized is at the same level with the declining RE technology cost rate and it is not retroactively applied to RE projects.

The adoption of alternative support mechanisms for the promotion of RES, including premium and tendering schemes, may increase the market design risk as the remuneration level will not be secured and there is no previous experience in the country. In addition, the policy design risk is expected to be reduced along with the sudden policy change risk element as the remuneration level for RE plants will be formulated in the energy market or via competitive bidding procedures. Thus, the interviewees estimated that the new policy mechanisms will lead in a competitive market with additional investments in new RE projects and less policy costs to the energy system.

Interviewees highlighted the need for the adoption of a clear and solid energy policy and strategy as a key policy priority, as well as, the convergence of actions of the national energy actors with the respective European bodies and the related Directives, in order to increase investors' trustfulness and, thus, RE investments' attractiveness. Within this framework, the formulation of a solid energy policy and strategy towards a sustainable energy transition is more than necessary in order to mitigate risks and related costs (Newbery, 2016; IRENA, 2015;

Ondraczek et al., 2015; IRENA, 2013; Wustenhagen and Menichetti, 2012; Masini and Menichetti, 2012; Saidur et al., 2010; Doukas et al., 2008).

Interviewees' feedback supports also the statement that the development of a solid regulatory framework, via the establishment of the Law 4414/2016, constitutes a cornerstone of the sustainable energy transition currently taking place in Greece. In addition, the shift from guaranteed remuneration mechanisms to market-based support schemes for the newly developed RE projects constitutes a significant policy action towards the considerable reduction of the policy design risk.

Another major challenge identified is the enhancement of citizens' confidence towards the extended implementation of RE projects. Therefore, the course of action of local and regional authorities is considered as a crucial parameter to be further promoted as their role is deemed critical in the further exploitation of the RE potential in the Greek territory. Within this framework, these authorities may become clean energy producers for their own needs and facilitate partnerships with the private sector via the contribution of land and water use rights. In addition, these authorities may persuade citizens not to resist against RE projects in their regions, through the implementation of relevant information campaigns and social actions.

As a major barrier for the extended deployment of RE projects in Greece, the "shock" to RE producers from the retroactive changes of the FIT levels, especially, for solar PV plants that took place in 2014, was identified by almost all interviewees. The second most significant barrier identified was the adverse economic environment and the financial crisis in Greece, with the reduced liquidity and the lack of available debt capital in the national investment environment to be the greatest components.

4.3 Financial Indicators

In total, the numerical values of the key financial indicators for onshore wind power projects in Greece, both extracted based on the theoretical methodology presented in Section 3 and

determined by the interviews' participants, for the years 2015 and 2016, are included in Table 5.

Table 5. Financial indicators of an onshore wind power project in Greece based on model and interviews

A deviation between the values calculated according to the theoretical model and the perceptions and views of the energy experts is depicted. Notable differences between the interview and the model results have been also identified in related interviews conducted in other EU countries.

These differences justified the necessity of interviews' conduction, in order to capture more realistically the investment environment for renewables in Greece and, thus, enhance the credibility of the extracted values. Regarding the evolution of the financial indicators from 2015 to 2016, a slight improvement of the respective indices is depicted, thus, reflecting a more secure investment environment. In particular, the cost of debt and the debt-to-equity ratio have shown improvement and the cost of equity remained almost at the same range, resulting into slightly lower values for the WACC. This can be explained by the fact that the economic environment in the country has been stabilized and the onshore wind project developers have ensured more favorable terms for the financing of their projects by debt providers.

Based on the existing literature, the WACC values for RE investments within the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries are typically in the range of 6% and 12% (UNDP, 2014).

Along with the onshore wind projects, numerical values for the identified financial indicators and related feedback have been also collected for the case of solar PV projects in Greece (Table 6).

Table 6. Financial indicators of a solar PV power project in Greece based on model and interviews

The WACC for solar PV power plants (>1 MW) is considered by experts to be 1%, or maximum 1.5%, higher than the respective WACC for onshore wind power plants in Greece. This difference is probably time-dependent as the interviews took place in 2014 and 2015 and the participants' perception was affected by the so-called "New deal" (Law 4254/2014), which has retroactively reduced the FIT of existing solar PV power plants. Furthermore, the cost of equity has been set a bit higher for solar PV projects and the cost of debt has been noted by interviewees at the same level as for onshore wind projects in Greece. Finally, for the case of the debt-to-equity ratio, values equal to 60/40, or even 50/50, have been considered for solar PV projects by interviews' participants. For the year 2016, all cost of capital components of the solar PV projects have been improved, illustrating a more stable environment for solar investments. In particular, the values of the cost of equity and the WACC have been considerably reduced from the previous year (2015), due to the "New Deal" Greek Law. The cost of capital is considered to be little lower for solar PV projects compared to onshore wind energy projects for the year 2016.

4.4 Discussion

Based on the feedback received from these series of interviews, a discussion on the results' comparison between the theoretical model and the key experts' choices is provided in the current subsection.

Specifically, the WACC was considered lower or equal to the extracted model results for the case of large-scale onshore wind projects. In addition, some interviewees expressed their views that the WACC might be little higher for small-scale projects and for RE projects connected to the High Voltage power grid. About large-scale solar PV projects, interviewees expressed both higher (14.5-15%) and lower (near 10%) values than the model ones.

Most of the interview participants noted that the cost of equity is lower than the one extracted from the model, at the range of 14-17%, for both RE technologies. This indicator is considered to be a little higher for large-scale solar PV power plants.

There was a general agreement about the level of the cost of debt for onshore wind and solar PV power plants, resulting to lower values than the respective model results. In particular, interviewees proposed values of the cost of debt between 8.5% (or even 6%) to a maximum of 12.5% and identified a little difference between the examined RE technologies.

Based on the bank investment policies and the lack of liquidity, as a consequence of the overall financial crisis, the debt-to-equity ratio of RE investments has changed considerably during the last years and, thus, the general case of 70/30 has been replaced by lower values. Moreover, some interviewees expressed their views that this ratio is generally affected by the project specifications (e.g. project and company size), as larger companies and bigger projects may gain easier funding via the provision of soft loans by banks. In addition, it was noted that this indicator is highly driven by the enterprises' creditworthiness and active involvement in the market, as companies with important track record, may achieve greater leverage of debt capital. Furthermore, the energy production from PVs is considered more guaranteed and, thus, these projects may be more easily financed by financial institutions. This is also the case for the RE projects installed on the non-interconnected islands, which are receiving higher returns than those connected to the interconnected power system in Greece. Moreover, guarantees in assets are required by financial institutions in order to provide the necessary liquidity to private investors, adding another constraint in the extended development of RE projects.

5. Conclusions

Within this study, a comprehensive assessment of the risk elements of RE investments, a quantification of the respective cost of capital and an evaluation of the adopted policies along with their impact on these investments in Greece have been attempted. A theoretical modelling approach was formed, as well as, a structured consultation process was elaborated with the participation of key national energy stakeholders.

Based on these research findings, the policy design risk constitutes the main influential parameter in the formulation of the cost of capital that exerts a considerable impact on RE

investments' implementation, followed by RE financing risk. Social acceptance risk has been also identified more significant for large-scale RE, mainly onshore wind, investments. Regarding the WACC indicator, values of 12% and up to 13.5% have been estimated for onshore wind and solar PV investments in Greece, in 2015, respectively. For the year 2016, the reduced WACC for solar PV projects, which is slightly lower than that of the onshore wind investments, reflect the gradual improvement of the investment environment in the national RE market. It is also worth to note that the country risk has been recognized as the greatest risk element for RE projects that is, however, driven by the economic environment in the country and may not be affected and mitigated via relevant policy actions on a national level.

The outcomes of current paper are followed by a set of implications for further policy consideration. Research conducted confirms that the design of the energy policy measures constitutes one of the most critical influential parameters in the risk mitigation of these projects. Therefore, a clear and stable policy framework may result into less risk and, thus, costs of RE projects development. In this context, the establishment of the Greek Law 4414/2016 is considered as a first critical step towards this direction and the market orientation of new RE installments is deemed not only a challenge but also a great opportunity for their future evolution. In addition, the essential role of local and regional authorities is highlighted towards the promotion and further enhancement of distributed RE penetration.

Further analysis of the cost of capital for other RE technologies (e.g. biomass) and energy sectors (e.g. heating/cooling, transport) could provide fruitful policy conclusions. In addition, the assessment of the cost of capital could be investigated at a regional level in Greece, highlighting also the two different areas identified, namely the mainland and the non-interconnected power systems.

The outcomes and policy implications of the current research may be efficiently exploited by EU countries with similar RE (high solar and wind potential) or economic characteristics, such as countries of the Mediterranean and Southeastern Europe.

In addition, the extension of the current methodological framework to energy efficiency investments is strongly recommended. Finally, a field of future research may be the examination and comparison of the different support mechanisms for RE investments in terms of cost-efficiency and induced policy costs to the energy market.

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Appendix A. Interviews' Questionnaire Template

Part 1: Renewable energy investment risks

The Cost of Equity is assumed as the sum of a baseline rate plus risk premiums for project risks. Nine risk categories have been identified that would be influencing the Cost of Equity.

In your opinion:

- a. Are there any risks missing?
- b. What category has the highest and the lowest impact on the Cost of Equity?
- c. Could you give basis points to the individual risks?
- d. If not, can you rank one over the other?

Part 2: Policy related risks

- a. Which renewable energy policy measures or changes of the last five years have changed the risk rates? Can you quantify the impact in basis points?
- b. How effective are the current renewable energy policies in reducing the renewable energy investment risks? Could you rate this on a scale from 1-5 (1=having no influence at all, 5=reducing the whole risk) or quantify them in basis points?

Part 3: Model results

In the last part of this interview, we would like to share some of our assumptions and results with you, to test how these compare to your estimations.

1. Debt/Equity ratio

- a. In order to calculate the WACC (Weighted Average Cost of Capital) we assumed that the project is financed with 70% Debt and 30% Equity. Do you find this ratio reasonable? Have you observed something else?
- b. Which factors exert the highest influence on the Debt/Equity ratio of a project?

2. Total WACC

Term	Description
WACC	Onshore wind: 13.5%

- a. Do you agree with our estimation of the WACC? Should it be lower / higher?
- b. Does this WACC change in your projects (depending on the country, technology, project size, etc.)?
- c. Do you expect higher or lower WACC for a large scale PV power plant (>1MW) and/or off-shore wind projects? How would the WACC change?

3. Cost of Equity:

To estimate the Cost of Equity, the following assumptions and data have been used:

$$\text{Cost of Equity} = \text{Risk-free rate} + \text{beta} * (\text{Market risk premium})$$

In which:

Term	Description
Risk free rate:	10 year Greek government bond
Market risk premium:	7.3%
Cost of Equity:	20.7% (wind onshore)

- a. Do you agree with our estimation of the Cost of Equity for an onshore wind project in Greece? Would you say that the Cost of Equity for Greece is higher or lower? Can you indicate how much higher or lower?

- b. Do you expect higher or lower Cost of Equity for a large scale PV power plant (>1MW)? How would the Cost of Equity change?

4. Cost of Debt:

To estimate the Cost of Debt, the following assumptions and data have been used:

$$\text{Cost of Debt} = \text{Risk free rate} + \text{Country risk spread} + \text{Renewable energy project spread}$$

In which:

Term	Description
Risk-free rate:	2.7% zero swap curve (10 years maturity)
Country risk spread:	8.5%
Renewable energy project spread:	3% onshore wind, 3.5% PV
Debt term	10 years
Cost of Debt:	onshore wind: 9.5-14.2% PV: 10-14.7%

- a. Do you agree with our estimation of the Cost of Debt? Should it be lower / higher?
 b. How many basis points do you add for the solar PV technology?

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Table 1. Remuneration levels for wind and solar PV power projects in Greece (€/MWh) – Based on Law 4414/2016

Renewable Energy Technologies	New Support Scheme – Reference Values valid from 2016^a
Onshore Wind ^{b,c}	98
Solar PVs on roof-tops (up to 10kW)	105 (from February 2017)
Solar PVs (P < 100 kW)	1.4xSMP ^d _{v-1}
Solar PVs (100 kW < P < 500kW)	1.3xSMP ^d _{v-1}
Solar PVs (P > 500 kW)	Via auction procedures

^aWithout support grants

^bMainland power system

^cNon-interconnected islands

^dAverage System Marginal Price

Sources: Governmental Gazette A 146/09-08-2016; Governmental Gazette 1103/02-05-2013.

Table 2. Calculation formulas of the financial indicators

Financial Indicators	Components
$WACC = \frac{E}{E + D} * CoE + \frac{D}{E + D} * CoD * (1 - Tax)$ <p>CoE = RfR + beta * MRP</p> <p>CoD = European RfR + CDS + PS</p> <p>or</p> <p>CoD = TS + CR + PS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ WACC: Weighted Average Cost of Capital ▪ E: Market Value of Equity ▪ D: Market Value of Debt ▪ CoE: Cost of Equity ▪ CoD: Cost of Debt ▪ Tax: Corporate Tax Rate ▪ CoE: Cost of Equity ▪ RfR: Risk-free Rate ▪ beta: beta Coefficient ▪ MRP: Market Risk Premium ▪ CoD: Cost of Debt ▪ European RfR: Risk-free Rate at EU-level ▪ CDS: 10-year Credit Default Spread of the Examined Country ▪ PS: Renewable Energy Project Spread or ▪ CoD: Cost of Debt ▪ TS: Term Swap Interest Rate ▪ CR: Country Risk ▪ PS: Renewable Energy Project Spread

Sources: Frank and Shen, 2015; Sharpe, 1964; Lintner, 1965; Eurelectric, 2012.

Table 3. Input data for the cost of capital calculation model

Parameters	Values
Risk-free Rate	10.05%
Beta	1.45
Market Risk Premium (MRP)	7.3%
Term Swap Interest Rate	2.68%
Country Risk	8.48%
Project Spread – Onshore wind	3%
Project Spread – Solar PV	3.5%
Debt-to-Equity ratio	70/30

Sources: Fernandez et al., 2013; Levin, 2012; Klessmann, 2013.

Table 4. Premiums for the risk elements based on interviews

Risk Elements	Interview Values
Social acceptance	1.5%
Administrative	0.5-2%
RE Financing	3-4%
Technical/Management	0%
Grid Access	0.5-1%
Policy design	3.5-5%
Market design and regulatory	0.5%
Sudden policy change	0-2.5%

Table 5. Financial indicators of an onshore wind power project in Greece based on model and interviews

Financial Indicator	Model Values (Year 2014)	Interviews Values (Year 2015)	Interviews Values (Year 2016)
WACC	13.5%	12%	10-12%
Cost of Equity	20.7%	14-16%	11-18%
Cost of Debt	9.5-14.2%	8.5-12.5%	6-8%
Debt-to-Equity ratio	70/30	55/45	60-70/30-40

Table 6. Financial indicators of a solar PV power project in Greece based on model and interviews

Financial Indicator	Model Values (Year 2014)	Interviews Values (Year 2015)	Interview Values (Year 2016)
WACC	13.8%	13-13.5%	7-12%
Cost of Equity	20.7%	14-17%	10-15%
Cost of Debt	10-14.7%	8.5-12.5%	6-12%
Debt-to-Equity ratio	70/30	55/45	60/40

Figure 1. National share of fuels in gross inland energy consumption, 2015 – total consumption for 2015: 24.4 Mtoe

Source: Eurostat (2017)

Figure 2. Shares of energy sources in the gross final electricity consumption in Greece, 2016
Source: LAGIE (2017)

Figure 3. Cumulative installed onshore wind power capacity (in MW) in Greece

Source: IRENA Resource (2016)

Figure 4. Net additions of annual installed onshore wind power capacity (in MW) in Greece
Source: IRENA Resource (2016)

Figure 5. Cumulative installed solar PV power capacity (in MW) in Greece
Source: IRENA Resource (2016)

Figure 6. Net additions of annual installed solar PV power installed capacity (in MW) in Greece
Source: IRENA Resource (2016)

Figure 7. Renewable energy risk elements

Source: DIA-CORE (2016)

Figure 8. Importance of renewable energy risk elements as ranked by interviewees